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MINERAL COMPOSITION OF ANCIENT CERAMICS FROM FUZULI DISTRICT

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TG/DTG, PXRD and TL methods were used to study four ancient pottery shards obtained from Leletepe archaeological site in Fizuli Province, Azerbaijan. This monument is of great importance for the Neolithic-Eneolithic period and is located in the Caucasus region.

Separate fragments of ceramic samples were submitted by the Institute of Archaeology and Anthropology of ANAS, discovered during the "Karabakh Neolithic-Eneolithic Expedition". The specimens are labeled as N1, N2, N3 and N4. These artifacts presumably belong to the Neolithic Age. The samples were exposed to Ni-filtered CuK α radiation with a wavelength of 1.5406 Å. The orientation of the samples was arbitrary. Scanning was performed at a rate of 1.2 degrees per minute over the range 5° to 75° (2 θ). Semi-quantitative metrics were derived from the PXRD data to assess the prevalence of mineral phases. Ceramic powders were subjected to thermogravimetric and differential thermal analysis using a Perkin Elmer STA6000 synchronous thermal analyzer. The analysis was performed at the following parameters: heating ranges from room temperature to 950°C, heating rate 5°C, scale sensitivity 0.1 μ g, and nitrogen gas flow rate 20 mL/min. All of the ancient pottery samples examined contain the minerals quartz and feldspar, albite in different proportions (Table 1). The results of XRD analysis showed that samples N1 and N4 contain diopside, while samples N2 and N3 contain maghemite. The absence of these minerals in the composition of the unprocessed ceramic material indicates a possible difference between the sources of ancient ceramic fragments and modern samples.

Table 1

Mineral composition of ancient ceramic samples

Sample	Quartz, mass %	Feldspar, mass %	Calcite, mass %	Clay minerals, mass %	Other minerals, mass %
N1	48.9	Albite -31.3	0	Muscovite -8.9	Diopside -10.4
2	54.8	Albite -29.3	3.7	Muscovite -10.3	Maghemite -1.9
N3	40.0	Albite-29.8	1.9	Muscovite -27.1	Maghemite -1.2
N4	29.1	Albite-39.0	8.6	Muscovite -7.3	Diopside -16.0

Table 1 shows that mullite was not detected in the samples of ceramics by XRD analysis. The absence of this mineral is also one of the factors used to determine the firing temperature of ancient ceramics, since it is formed during the high-temperature firing of kaolinite. It can serve as an indicator of the maximum firing temperature reached during the production of ancient ceramics. During firing, mullite, cristobalite and hematite are formed, associated with helenite and anorthite at temperatures above 1150°C. Consequently, we can say with a high degree of certainty that the samples of ancient ceramics were made at temperatures below 950°C. At temperatures above 600°C, montmorillonite transforms into an amorphous phase and can be used as a reference for determining the minimum temperature at which ceramics can be fired. Differential thermal curves of maghemite show a prominent peak at 815°C. An X-ray diffraction (XRD) study identified the maghemite peak, however, this fact means little to determine the maximum firing temperature of the ancient pottery. Although only three of the four ancient pottery samples contain calcite, it is assumed that the firing process in all four of these samples ceased when the temperature reached 700°C.